

**Highly Sensitive and Rapid Determination of Escherichia coli O157:H7 in Minced
Beef and Water using Electrocatalytic Gold Nanoparticle Tags**

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ABSTRACT

A simple, highly sensitive and specific immunosensing assay for rapid detection and quantification of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 in meat and water samples based on the electrocatalytic properties of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) towards hydrogen evolution reaction and superparamagnetic microbeads (MBs) as pre-concentration/purification platforms without the need of broth enrichment is developed for the first time. Minced beef and water samples inoculated with different concentrations of *E. coli* O157:H7 have been tested using anti-*E. coli* O157- magnetic beads conjugate (MBs-pECAb) as a capture platform and sandwiching afterwards with AuNPs modified with secondary antibodies (AuNPs-sECAb) and detected using chronoamperometric measurement with screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs). Detection limits (LOD) of 148, 457 and 309 CFU/mL were obtained in buffer solution, minced beef and tap water samples respectively, with a broad detection range of 10^2 - 10^5 CFU/mL in all cases. Recoveries percentages after spiking of 5 different samples of both minced beef and tap water with 10^3 and 10^4 CFU/mL were 94.7 & 90.4 (in beef) and 91.3 & 94.8 % (in water), respectively. Specificity, reproducibility and comparison with a commercial lateral flow kit in terms of LOD and detection range were also studied showing clear advantages of the electrochemical method performance. The successful application of this AuNPs based technology in minced beef and tap water indicates the possibility of its using in various food items and other water resources.

KEYWORDS: *E. coli* O157:H7, gold nanoparticles, Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), electrochemical biosensor, minced beef.

1. INTRODUCTION

Escherichia coli O157:H7 is a type of enterohemorrhagic, Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (EHEC, STEC) first discovered in 1982 which normally lives in the intestines of humans and other animals. It has emerged as an important enteric highly infective food and water borne pathogen posing a tremendous challenge to public health. Illnesses caused by *E. coli* O157:H7 can range from mild, watery diarrhea to life-threatening conditions, such as hemolytic uremic syndrome (in 2-7% of cases) and hemorrhagic colitis especially in children and elderly [Jay et al., 2000; World Health Organization, 2006]. It has been stated that the presence of *E. coli* O157:H7 at or above 1 CFU/25 g constitutes adulterated and dangerous ground beef, which corresponds to a dose of *E. coli* O157:H7 of 10–100 cells [FDA, 2011].

High levels of competing microflora in food and water samples compound the difficulty of isolating *E. coli* O157:H7. The common isolation methods using selective culturing media can take more than 48 h to complete and still require expert judgment and further testing to confirm its presence [Johnson et al., 1998]. Immunoassay methods which yield a presumptive positive or negative screening result in 24h or less have been developed. Typical sensitivities of immunoassays are approximately 10^6 CFU/mL, which may lead to false-negative results, particularly when initial levels of competing flora reach 10^5 to 10^6 CFU/g [Firstenberg-Eden et al., 1997] a situation not uncommon in ground beef. Since standard methods of identifying *E. coli* O157:H7 require at least a full day (to rule out a negative sample) and up to several days (to confirm a positive result) and employ highly qualified persons in highly specialized laboratories. Consequently, sensitive, rapid and simple methods are required.

Biosensor technologies play an increasingly important role in the detection of pathogenic bacteria because they have great potential to satisfy the practical need for rapid, sensitive, easy to use, portable, and low-cost detection [Liébana et al., 2009; Navak et al., 2008; Afonso et al., 2013]. Biosensor technology coupled with the use of nanoparticles (NPs) tags and other nanomaterials offers benefits compared to traditional methods in terms of time of analysis, sensitivity and simplicity [Mao et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2009].

The objective of this work is to develop a rapid electrochemical biosensing strategy for *E. coli* O157:H7 quantification in real food samples (minced beef and tap water) using specific antibodies labeled with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and magnetic beads (MBs) capture platforms in liquid suspensions. AuNPs have been shown as excellent labels in both optical (e.g., ELISA) and electrochemical (e.g., differential pulse voltammetric) detection of DNA [Pumera et al., Langmuir 2005] and proteins [Ambrosi et al., 2007; Ambrosi et al., 2010]. The use of the electrocatalytic properties of the AuNPs on hydrogen formation from hydrogen ions (hydrogen evolution reaction, HER) also enables an enhanced quantification of nanoparticles [Maltez da Costa et al., 2010] allowing the detection of proteins [De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2009a; De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2010] and cells [De la Escosura-Muñiz et al. 2009b; Maltez da Costa et al., 2012ab] of clinical interest through their labeling with nanoparticle conjugates. However, this technology has not been used yet for the screening of any kind of bacteria in real samples.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Materials

Dynabeads anti-E.coli O157 (superparamagnetic polystyrene microscopic beads modified with E. coli O157 primary antibody) (MBs-pECAb) 2.8 µm sized (Prod. no.710.03) were purchased from Invitrogen Dynal Biotech AS (Oslo, Norway). Escherichia coli O157:H7 (CECT 4783) and Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar typhimurium LT2 (CECT 722T) strains were obtained from “Colección Española de Cultivos Tipo (CECT)”. Both bacterial strains and inocula were prepared following a standard procedure, as detailed in the *supplementary material*.

20 nm gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were synthesized by reducing tetrachloroauric acid with trisodium citrate, a method pioneered by Turkevich [Turkevich et al., 1951] and were modified with antibodies according a procedure previously optimized by our group [Ambrosi et al., 2007]. The detailed experimental procedure for AuNPs synthesis and bioconjugation, together to TEM images is available at the *supplementary material*.

Antibodies, general reagents and apparatus and electrodes used in this work are also detailed in the *supplementary material*.

2.2. Methods

Preparation of minced beef samples

Minced beef samples were obtained from local retail butcher shop and analyzed by standard culturing method [International Organization for Standardization] for the presence of E. coli O157:H7, and only negative samples were selected to be spiked by bacteria. 10 g of E. coli O157:H7 free minced beef were homogenized with 90 mL of sterile PBST in a

stomacher (Lab Blender 400, Seward, UK) during 3 minutes. Beef extract was purified by centrifugation (1000 rpm/5 min) to remove large particles then used as a diluent to prepare different bacterial concentrations.

Spike and recovery protocol

Spike and recovery experiment is important method for validating and assessing the accuracy of an analytical technique for particular sample types. It was done to determine whether E. coli O157:H7 detection is affected by a difference between the diluent used to prepare the standard curve (PBST) and the biological sample matrix (minced beef and tap water). This experiment was performed by spiking of PBST, minced beef and tap water with 10^3 and 10^4 CFU/mL of E .coli O157:H7 (n= 3 for each sample), then the spiked samples were evaluated under the same condition in a single experiment. After that the recovery % of bacteria from minced beef and tap water samples was obtained as comparing with PBST results.

Magnetosandwich assay using gold nanoparticle (AuNP) labels and electrocatalytic detection

The magnetosandwich assay was performed following a methodology previously optimized in our group [Ambrosi et al. 2007; Afonso et al. 2013], with some variations. Briefly, 15 μ L stock solution of previously washed MBs-pECAb was incubated for 5 h/25 °C under gentle stirring in a thermoShaker, with 135 μ L casein sodium salt 5 % then kept overnight in the fridge. The blocked MBs-pECAb were incubated with 150 μ L of heat killed E. coli O157:H7 (different concentrations) for 30 min/25 °C/650 rpm. After that MBs-pECAb/EC complex was magnetically separated from solution, and washed with WB and PBS buffer. A blank PBST was used as blank for this assay. The last incubation step with the previously

prepared AuNPs-sECAb conjugate, was performed under the same conditions of the previous incubation with subsequently washing steps, resulting in complete magnetosandwich that is ready to be analyzed (figure 1A).

[Preferred position for figure 1]

Quantitative analyses were carried out following the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) catalyzed by the AuNPs, taking advantage of the chronoamperometric mode [Maltez da Costa et al., 2010]. Chronoamperograms were obtained by placing a mixture of 25 μ L of 1 M HCl and 25 μ L of the magnetosandwich solution (performed for PBST, beef extract and tap water containing different concentrations of the target bacteria) onto the surface of the electrodes (figure 1B) and, subsequently, holding the working electrode at a potential of +1.35 V for 1 min and then applying a negative potential of -1.00 V for 100 sec, recording the cathodic current generated which constitutes the analytical signal. A new electrode was employed for each measurement. This value of potential applied during a fixed time (-1.00 V; 100s) was previously optimized through cyclic voltammetric studies (figure 1C; see detailed explanation at the *supplementary material*).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Electrochemical detection of E. coli O157:H7

MBs-pECAb and MBs-pECAb/EC conjugates were first characterized by SEM analysis. Figure 1D illustrates the immunological attachment of E. coli O157 to the MBs-pECAb forming MBs-pECAb/EC conjugates (more SEM figures for the conjugate are available at the *supplementary material*).

After optimization of the adequate antibody to form the specific sandwich with the MBs/EC complex (goat polyclonal antibody ab30521) and of the blocking agent for avoiding unspecific absorption (5% casein) (see detailed optimization studies at the *supplementary material*), *E. coli* O157:H7 containing samples were analyzed by the electrochemical method. Figure 2A-B shows the results of electrochemical determination of *E. coli* O157:H7 in PBST. The mean currents obtained for increasing concentrations of bacteria (10^2 - 10^7 CFU/mL) show a gradual increasing (from 10^2 to 10^5 CFU/mL) with a logarithmic response from 10^2 to 10^4 (correlation coefficient, $r \approx 1$). From this logarithmic relationship it can be estimated a detection limit (LOD) of 148 CFU/mL (calculated as the CFU/mL which gives a signal equal to the mean signal of the blank + 3 times its standard deviation).

[Preferred position for figure 2]

This decline in the signal for bacterial concentrations higher than 10^5 could be related to the blocking of the electrode surface by the bacteria, hindering the electrocatalytic reaction. It could be concluded from the behavior of this dose-response relationship that the quantification of *E. coli* O157:H7 in unknown sample using this logarithmic range could be done by preparation of two tenfold serial dilutions from the original sample; increasing of the current by dilution indicates that *E. coli* O157:H7 concentration in the original sample is $> 10^5$, while decreasing of the current by dilution indicates that it is $\leq 10^5$ CFU/mL and consequently it can be quantified. This kind of decrease in the signal for saturated concentrations of bacteria was also observed using commercial available kits based on Lateral Flow Assays, as we explain at section 3.2 (see also figures SM-5 and SM-7 at the *supplementary material*). To evaluate the precision of the developed technique, five different samples of PBST spiked with 5×10^2 CFU/mL of *E. coli* O157:H7 were tested

under the same conditions in a single experiment. It was found a main value of the current of 27.9 μA and a RSD of 4.7 % which indicates good reproducibility of the developed system.

The specificity of the electrochemical immunoassay *versus* another bacterial spp. of the same “Enterobacteriaceae family” such as *Salmonella typhimurium* LT2 was demonstrated. For this study, we selected 10^4 CFU/mL which is the highest concentration of *E. coli* O157:H7 within the dynamic range of response of our system (see figures 2A and 2B). As shown in figure 2C the mean current values obtained by *E. coli* O157:H7 were higher than two folds of that obtained by *Salmonella typhimurium* (22 ± 1.5 and 46.7 ± 3.5 μA , respectively), while the later was approximately similar to that of blank PBST (17 ± 4.9 μA) which demonstrates that this method is highly selective for the target bacteria. Furthermore, the mean current value produced by the *E. coli* O157:H7 was almost similar to that of the sample containing both bacterial spp. which clarifies that the electrochemical signal is not affected by the presence of other competing bacterial spp. Regarding these slight differences in produced signal between blank PBST and *Salmonella* containing sample and also between *E. coli* containing sample and sample of the mixture can be related to a certain degree of cross reactivity and non-specific binding of the used antibody, due to the antigenic similarity between some bacterial spp. these antibodies could cross-react and bind to a limited extent with some spp. of *Salmonella*, *Proteus* and *Escherichia hermanii* [Invitrogen, 2008]. Nevertheless this level of interference does not affect the feasibility of the *E. coli* O157:H7 detection.

3.2. E. coli O157:H7 analysis in real samples: spike and recovery

While analysis in buffer solution is important, analysis in real samples with minimal sample preparation is the main goal. Different concentrations of E. coli O157:H7 ($10 - 10^7$ CFU/mL) were prepared in minced beef extract and tap water as described previously. As shown in figure 2D, the obtained results for increasing concentrations of the target analyte in minced beef showed a logarithmic range (from $10^2 - 10^5$ CFU/mL with $r = 0.979$). Similar results to those of minced beef were obtained in tap water samples (logarithmic range from $10^2 - 10^5$ CFU/mL with $r = 0.985$). The estimated LOD were 457 and 309 CFU/mL, respectively, which are lower than the reported using alternative rapid advanced technologies (see table SM-1 at the *supplementary material*)

In order to compare the limit of detection of the developed assay with available rapid methods, RapidChek® E. coli O157 (including H7) Lateral Flow Assay was used for this comparison. The performance of these kits was reviewed by AOAC Research Institute and approved as a tool for detection of E. coli O157:H7 in food samples [Sdix. Rapidcheck, 2011]. The limit of detection of the commercial test assay was evaluated in PBST, minced beef and tap water samples using the same samples used for the electrochemical immunoassay. It was found that LOD by the commercial kits was 10^5 CFU/mL in each of PBST, minced beef and tap water samples (see figures: SM-5, 6 & 7 at the *supplementary material*), it means that LOD was improved by about 1000, 200 and 300-fold by the electrochemical immunoassay, respectively. Furthermore, a decrease in the signal for saturating concentrations of E. coli O157:H7 was also observed (figures SM-5 and SM-7), which is in concordance with the electrochemical observations, as mentioned in section 3.1. Spike and recovery experiment was performed to determine whether E. coli O157:H7 detection is affected by the biological sample matrix of both minced beef and water. The

data showed in table 1 summarizes the results of spike and recovery experiment of E. coli O157:H7 in both samples.

[Preferred position for table 1]

It is clear that recovery rate of the target bacteria was 94.7 and 90.4 % from minced beef samples and 91.3 and 94.8 % from tap water samples for spiked amount of 10^3 and 10^4 CFU/mL, respectively. These high recovery rates demonstrate that this technology is a promising alternative for determination of E. coli O157:H7 in such samples.

In order to determine E. coli O157:H7 in real unknown non-spiked minced beef samples using this technology, it is recommended that 25 g of sample should be homogenized with 225 mL of sterile TSB using a stomacher for 3 minutes, then two tenfold serial dilutions are prepared from the original dilution and incubated at 37 °C/ 8 h, then centrifuge the samples at 1000 rpm/ 5 min to remove the solid particles. Finally, 150 μ L of each dilution could be used directly for immunosandwich preparation. Regarding the application in water samples, the same as in minced beef but without homogenization is recommended.

In contrast, the time required to carry out the electrochemical technique (from sampling until quantification) is approximately 9-10 hours (8 h. for enrichment + 30 min. for each incubation with MBs-pECAb and AuNPs-sECAb + 30 minutes for magnetic separation and washing). This is a great advantage over the standard method, which requires 24 h even for an initial positive/negative result [FDA, 2011]. Moreover, this assay time (70 - 90 min.) is competitive in comparison with other electrochemical detection methods (120 min. for IMS then label-free amperometric detection [Pérez et al., 1998] and IMS, enzymatic label and amperometric detection [Ruan et al., 2002]).

Another important advantage of this biosensor is its portability. The handheld potentiostat can be paired with a pocket PC, battery-operated, and transported easily. All the other

necessary equipment and reagents can also be transported and operated remotely, which enables the possibility of field analysis using this biosensor.

Because of the low infective dose of *E. coli* O157:H7 and low levels naturally present in foods with uneven distribution, enrichment stage is still required for the detection of this organism by any technology. The estimated LOD in this study without broth enrichment by our assay confirms the possibility of detecting *E. coli* O157:H7 at much lower concentrations within the infective dose (10-100 CFU) reported by FDA [FDA, 2011] after 8 h of sample enrichment.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the electrocatalytic properties of AuNPs towards HER in combination with magnetic beads as a pre-concentrator showed a high sensitivity rate in detection of *E. coli* in beef and water samples. The developed assay can detect *E. coli* O157:H7 in both beef and water samples without broth enrichment at a much lower concentration (457 and 309 CFU/mL respectively) than other previously reported advanced technologies within shorter time (70-80 min). The selection of the optimum antibody for specifically recognizing the bacteria strain after the magnetic capturing together with the adequate blocking agent for avoiding unspecific absorptions are key findings for the success of the analytical method. Furthermore, this method showed a high specificity rate when tested against *Salmonella typhimurium*, in addition to high sensitivity rate in the presence of other competing bacteria. The accuracy of the designed immunosensor was good with a variation coefficient equals 6.7 %, moreover a high recovery rates (94.7 and 90.4 % from minced beef samples and 91.3 and 94.8 % from tap water samples for spiked amount of 10^3 and 10^4 CFU/mL, respectively) were obtained. Several advantages were observed in this technology

compared to the previously reported ones (see table 1) regarding to limit of detection, simplicity, rapid assay duration, high accuracy, selectivity and high specificity in the presence of other competing bacterial spp. The high complexity of beef as a food matrix indicates the possibility of using this technology in various food items also other water resources. The possibility to avoid broth enrichment together with the use of portable handheld potentiostat paired with a pocket PC enables rapid in-field analysis of food and water samples without the need for highly equipped and specialized laboratories.

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FIGURE AND TABLE CAPTIONS

Fig 1. Schematic experimental design. (A) *E. coli* O157:H7 was captured by MBs-pECAb and subsequently labelled with AuNPs-sECAb in the presence of control bacteria (*Salmonella typhimurium*). (B) Left: Detection of labeled *E. coli* O157:H7 through the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) electrocatalyzed by the AuNP labels. Right: Chronoamperograms registered in 1M HCl, during the HER applying a constant voltage of -1.0V for increasing *E. coli* O157:H7 concentrations (from top to bottom: 0, 10^2 , 5×10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 and 10^5 CFU/mL). (C) Cyclic voltammograms recorded from +1.25V to 0V in 1M HCl for 0 (red curve) and 10^5 (blue curve) CFU/mL; scan rate: 50 mV/s. (D) SEM image for heat-killed *E. coli* O157:H7 (left) and MBs-pECAb before (center) and after (right) incubation with 10^5 CFU/mL of *E. coli* O157:H7 (Bacteria are pointed by red arrows).

Fig. 2. (A) Electrochemical results obtained by blank PBST and different concentrations of *E. coli* O157:H7 in PBST (10^2 till 10^7 CFU/mL). (B) Logarithmic range of the dose-response relationship is from 10^2 till 10^4 CFU/mL ($r=1$). (C) Specificity study of the immunoassay in blank PBST and PBST inoculated by *Salmonella typhimurium* (10^4 CFU/mL), *E. coli* O157:H7 (10^4 CFU/mL), and a mixture of *E. coli* O157:H7 and *Salmonella typhimurium* (10^4 CFU/mL for each bacteria). (D) Logarithmic response of the current produced by 10^2 , 5×10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 and 10^5 CFU/mL in tap water (a) and minced beef extract (b). The error bars show standard deviation for three replicates.

Table 1. Spike and recovery assay data. The study was done by spiking 10^3 and 10^4 CFU/mL of *E. coli* O157:H7 in PBST, minced beef and tap water ($n= 3$ for each sample) and the recovery % of bacteria from real samples was obtained as comparing with PBST.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

TABLE 1

Samples	Spiked E. coli O157:H7 (CFU/mL)	Current in PBST (μA)	Current in real samples (μA)	Recovery (%)
	10^3	30.4	28.8	94.7
Minced beef	10^4	38.4	34.7	90.4
	10^3	30.4	27.7	91.3
Tap water	10^4	38.4	36.3	94.8

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Highly Sensitive and Rapid Determination of Escherichia coli O157:H7 in Minced Beef and Water using Electrocatalytic Gold Nanoparticle Tags

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Antibodies, general reagents, apparatus and electrodes

Anti- E. coli O157:H7 antibodies: goat polyclonal (sECAb) (Prod. no. ab30521), rabbit polyclonal (Prod. no. ab68451), goat polyclonal (Prod. no. ab25823) and mouse monoclonal (Prod. no. ab20976) were purchased from Abcam plc.

Bovine serum albumin (BSA), hydrogen tetrachloroaurate (III) trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%) and trisodium citrate ($\text{Na}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). PBST was used as a washing buffer consisted of 0.05% (v/v) tween-20 in 0.01 M phosphate buffered saline (PBS), pH 7.4. Blocking buffer for AuNPs/sECAb conjugate consisted of 1 mg/mL BSA (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) in milli-Q water (w/v) and blocking buffer for MBs/pECAb conjugate was casein sodium salt form bovine milk 5 % (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) in milli-Q water (w/v). Samples for SEM analysis were prepared by using glutaraldehyde and hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) microscopy grade solutions (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain). The electrochemical measurements were performed in analytical grade 1 M HCl solution (Merck, Spain) prepared in ultra-pure water. Unless otherwise stated, all reagents and other inorganic chemicals were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich or Fluka (Spain). All chemicals were used as received and all aqueous solutions were prepared in milli-Q water (Millipore purification system, 18.2 M Ω cm).

The electrochemical transducers used were homemade screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs), consisting of three electrodes: carbon working electrode (WE), Ag/AgCl reference electrode (RE) and carbon counter electrode (CE) in a single strip fabricated with a semi-automatic screen-printing machine DEK248 (DEK International, Switzerland) (figure SM-1). The materials and reagents used for this process were: Autostat HT5 polyester sheet (McDermid Autotype, UK), Electrodag 423SS carbon ink, Electrodag 6037SS silver/silver chloride ink and Minico 7000 Blue insulating ink (Acheson Industries,

The Netherlands). A magnet (3 mm in diameter), inserted under the WE, was also used to accumulate the magnetosandwich (MBs-pECAb/EC/sECAb-AuNPs) during the electrochemical measurements.

The electrochemical experiments were performed with a μ Autolab II (Echo Chemie, The Netherlands) potentiostat/galvanostat connected to a PC and controlled by Autolab GPES 4.9007 software (General Purpose Electrochemical System). All measurements were carried out at room temperature, with a working volume of 50 μ L, which was enough to cover the three electrodes contained in the SPCEs connected to the potentiostat by a homemade edge connector module.

Scanning electrochemical microscopy (SEM) images were acquired using a Scanning Electron Microscopy (MAGELLAN 400L XHR, FEI Company, Netherlands). A Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) Jeol JEM-2011 (Jeol Ltd., Japan) was used to characterize the gold nanoparticles. Commercial kit of RapidChek® E. coli O157 (including H7) lateral flow assay was purchased from Sdix (Newark, USA). Densimat is a densitometer designed specifically for inoculum standardization (bioMérieux SA, France). A thermoshaker TS1 (Biometra) was used to stir the samples operating at controlled temperature.

All glassware used in the synthesis of AuNPs was washed with aqua regia overnight and then rinsed carefully with milli-Q water.

Bacterial strains and inocula preparation

Salmonella typhimurium were revived in Tryptone Soy Broth (TSB, Oxoid Ltd., UK), incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and then transferred onto Tryptone Soy Agar plates (TSA, Oxoid Ltd., UK). Stock cultures of both strains were prepared on Tryptone Soy Agar

slopes, incubated for 24 h at 37 °C then stored at 4 °C for a maximum time of 8 weeks. Stock cultures were subcultured into 10 mL of TSB and incubated at 37 °C for 20 h. Afterwards, a loopful from the broth was spread using a disposable plastic loop on TSA plates and incubated at 37 °C for 20–24 h. Subsequently, cell suspensions were prepared directly in 5 mL sterile PBST and tap water, using bacterial colonies to obtain a bacterial load of 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL according to McFarland standards [McFarland, 1907] using DENSIMAT apparatus and then different bacterial concentrations (10 - 10^8 CFU/mL) were prepared from the original one. While in case of minced beef, 1 mL of sterile PBST contains 1.5×10^8 CFU was used to prepare different subsequent concentrations in beef extract. Tubes were placed into a boiling water bath (100 °C) for 15 min to kill the bacteria and stop replication and then were cooled to room temperature prior to refrigeration until using.

Synthesis and modification of gold nanoparticles

20 nm gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were synthesized by reducing tetrachloroauric acid with trisodium citrate, a method pioneered by Turkevich [Turkevich et al., 1951]. Briefly, AuNPs were synthesized by reducing tetrachloroauric acid with trisodium citrate, a method pioneered by Turkevich et al. (Turkevich et al., 1951). Briefly, 200 mL of 0.01% HAuCl_4 solution (25 mM) were boiled with vigorous stirring. 5 mL of 1% trisodium citrate solution were added quickly to the boiling solution. When the solution turned deep red, indicating the formation of AuNPs 20 nm sized, the solution was left stirring and cooling down.

The modification of AuNPs with goat polyclonal anti- *E. coli* O157:H7 antibodies was performed according to the following procedure, previously optimized by our group

[Ambrosi et al., 2007]: 1.75 mL of 20 nm AuNPs colloidal solution was mixed with 100 μ L (100 μ g/mL) of secondary polyclonal antibody solution and incubated at 25°C for 20 min. Subsequently, a blocking step with 150 μ L of 1 mg/mL BSA, incubating at 25 °C for 20 min was undertaken. Finally, a centrifugation at 14.000 rpm for 20 min was carried out, and AuNPs-sECAb conjugate was re-suspended in 2 mL milli-Q water.

Evaluation of AuNPs by TEM

TEM analysis of AuNPs was performed after dropping 4 μ L of AuNPs solution onto a copper disk. The sample was dried at room temperature during 2 hours, an essential condition for having good images. The images obtained by TEM were analyzed using the free software Image that allows the measurement of the nanoparticles size and enables the description during the statistical analysis.

Optimization of the potential applied for the chronoamperometric detection of AuNPs

This value of potential applied during a fixed time was optimized through cyclic voltammetric studies. As shown in figure 1C of the main text, the reduction of the medium's protons to hydrogen starts at approximately -0.60 V (red curve). In the presence of AuNPs (blue curve) on the surface of the electrode, the potential for hydrogen ion reduction shifts toward less negative potentials by up to 500 mV. Furthermore, it can also be observed that, due to the catalytic effect of the AuNPs, a higher current is generated (up to 100 μ A higher, as evaluated for the potential value of -1.40 V). The oxygen reduction on SPCE at very negative potentials (up to -1.40 V) is not of great importance; therefore, the background signals are not affected. If an adequate potential is fixed at i.e. -1.00 V, the

intensity of the current recorded in chronoamperometric mode during the stage of hydrogen ion electroreduction can be related to the presence or absence of AuNPs (and consequently of *E. coli* O157:H7) on the surface of the SPCE. Regarding the fixed interval of time selected for the current recording, it was observed that for intervals shorter than 100 s the current profiles were not reproducible (figure 1B). Looking at the behavior during the first 10 seconds, a dramatic decrease in the cathodic current was observed in the absence of AuNPs (background; red chronoamperogram), probably due to the lack of a protons reduction catalyzer, followed by a current stabilization. However, in the presence of the AuNPs (blue chronoamperograms), the current does not suffer such dramatic decrease, suggesting that the NP catalyzers keep a more constant rate of hydrogen generation from the first second. The certain irreproducibility observed during the 10-100 s range could be attributed to the AuNPs accommodation on the electrode surface conducted through the MBs under the magnetic field exerted by the magnet, which requires some stabilization time. This current was stable in all cases after 100s, so the absolute value of the current registered at this time was chosen as analytical signal.

Sample preparation for Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis

For heat killed *E. coli* O157:H7, MBs-pECAb conjugate and MBs-pECAb/EC complex; *E. coli* O157:H7 suspension of 10^5 CFU/mL of PBST was used. The same procedure as mentioned in the text for preparation of each complex was adopted. The complex was magnetically separated from the washing solution whereas bacteria alone were recovered by centrifugation and fixed with 2.5 % glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M cacodilate buffer during 1 h/25°C. After that the complex or bacteria pellet was dehydrated sequentially in ethanol

increasing series (30, 50 and 96 %, 5 min for each/25°C). To complete the dehydration process, samples were incubated three times in 100 % ethanol (5 min/ 25°C), and finally resuspended in hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) (Sigma-Aldrich) solution and kept at 4°C until analysis. The volume of all reagents used was always 10× the pellet volume, and slow agitation was performed to promote a better diffusion. Prior to SEM analysis (MAGELLAN 400L XHR, FEI Company, Netherlands), 4 µL of each sample were deposited onto a 0.5 × 0.5 mm silicon dioxide wafer placed over a typical SEM sample holder. This protocol is well suited for fixation of bacteria in suspension and avoids the use of metallization steps.

Optimization of the specific antibody and the blocking of MBs-pECAb conjugate

Since commercially available MBs-pECAb react with all E.coli O157 strains, a key point here consists in finding the adequate antibody to form the specific sandwich with the E. coli O157:H7 after the magnetic capturing. Different polyclonal and monoclonal antibodies conjugated to AuNPs were evaluated in the magnetosandwich immunoassay finding that goat polyclonal antibody ab30521 showed the best ability to recognize the target strain and consequently form the sandwich, so it was chosen for the bacteria quantification (see the detailed study at the *supporting information*). However, unspecific absorptions of the AuNPs-sECAb conjugate were observed after the magnetosandwich immunoassay, being required an adequate blocking of the free surface sites of the magnetic beads. The optimization of this step was done by evaluating different blocking reagents with different concentrations and variable incubation times (see the detailed procedure at the *supplementary material*). In this optimization each blocking reagent was tested separately

in a blank assay (without bacteria). Bovine serum albumin (BSA) at different concentrations (5 % and 10 %) in milli-Q water showed a high level of unspecific response (figure 2B). Therefore, different concentrations of casein (1, 2 and 5 %) in milli-Q water were also evaluated, obtaining for the 5% casein a signal almost as low as the background levels (current registered for 1M HCl solution), so it was chosen as optimum for reducing the unspecific reaction between MBs-pECAb and AuNPs-sECAb.

The explanation to such behavior could be related to the size and homogeneity of the blocking agent. An ideal blocking agent should be a macromolecule, large enough to stably attach onto the surface to be blocked but also small enough to find its way between the antibodies. BSA was shown as efficient blocking agent in previously reported magnetosandwich immunoassays where the antibody immobilization was performed on streptavidin-modified beads [De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2009a]. However, in the already antibody-modified beads (commercially available) used in the present work, the density of antibodies could be higher, so the large size of BSA (MW 67 kDa) could hinder its attachment to the beads surface. The lower size and higher heterogeneity of casein (casein subunits vary primarily in MW from 19 to 25 kDa) [Péterfi and Cocsis, 2000; Vogt et al., 1987] seems to be crucial here for reaching the beads surface, resulting in a more effective blocking.

Figure SM-1: (A) Detail of one SPCE, containing the three electrodes in the working area; R- Ag/AgCl reference electrode, W- carbon working electrode and C- carbon counter electrode. (B) Images of the 45 SPCE sensors sheet obtained following the experimental procedure.

Figure SM-2: (A) TEM image of the self-synthesized AuNPs and (B) the corresponding size-distribution diagram. (C) Chronoamperograms recorded at -1V in 1M HCl for different concentrations of AuNPs suspensions, from up to bottom: 0, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 8 pM and (D) the corresponding relationship between the absolute value of the cathodic current at 100 s and the concentration of AuNPs.

Figure SM-3: SEM image for *E. coli* O157:H7 bacteria conjugated with MBs- primary anti-*E. coli* O157 antibody (MBs-pECAb/EC complex) (Bacteria are pointed by red arrow).

Fig. SM4. (A) Optimization of the antibody used in the conjugate with AuNPs in a magnetosandwich assay for a fixed quantity of *E. coli* O157:H7 (10^3 CFU/mL). (B) Optimization of the blocking of MBs-pECAb conjugate. The error bars represent standard deviation for three replicates.

Figure SM-5: (A) Results of RapidCheck® E. coli O157 (including H7) lateral flow commercial kits for different concentrations of E. coli O157:H7 (10^3 - 10^8 CFU/mL) in PBST. The range of detection is 10^5 - 10^8 CFU/mL of E. coli O157:H7 with decreasing in the signal in concentrations higher than 10^7 . (B) Specificity study for the commercial kits against Salmonella typhimurium (10^6 CFU/mL PBST).

Figure SM-6: Results of RapidCheck® E. coli O157 (including H7) lateral flow commercial kits for different concentrations of E. coli O157:H7 (10^2 - 10^7 CFU/mL) in minced beef. The range of detection is 10^5 - 10^7 CFU/mL of E. coli O157:H7 with decreasing in the signal in concentrations higher than 10^7 .

Figure SM-7: Results of RapidCheck® E. coli O157 (including H7) lateral flow commercial kits for different concentrations of E. coli O157:H7 (10^2 - 10^8 CFU/mL) in tap water. The range of detection is 10^5 - 10^8 CFU/mL of E. coli O157:H7 with decreasing in the signal in concentrations higher than 10^7 .

Technology	Sample	Detection limit (CFU)	Ref.
RT multiplex PCR	Pure culture	225 per mL	Fratamico et al. 2010
RT SYBR [®] Green fluorescent PCR	Pure culture	8.4×10^3 per mL	Jothikumar et al., 2002
RT TaqMan PCR	Pure culture Ground beef	10^4 per mL 10^6 per g	Tsai et al. 2006
Flow cytometry	Ground beef, milk and apple juice	10^3 per g or mL	Yamaguchi et al. 2003
	Pure culture broth	10^4 per mL	Goodridge et al. 1999
ATP Bioluminescence	Milk	10^4 per mL	Samkutty et al. 2001
Amperometric	PBS	4.12×10^2 per mL	Li et al. 2012
Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy	Buffer	10^3 per mL	Li et al. 2011
	Buffer	10^2 per mL	Chowdhury et al. 2012
	Ground beef	1.2×10^3 per g	Varshney et al. 2007
	Buffer Lettuce wash water	10^4 per mL 10^7 per mL	Radke et al. 2005
Millimeter-sized PZT Cantilever	PBS	7×10^2 per mL	Campbell et al. 2005
IMS with Solid-phase cytometry Laser	Food and water	10^4 per mL	Pyle et al. 1999
Robotic fluorimetric assay system	PBS	10^5 per mL	Leskinen et al. 2009
FT-IR Spectroscopy	Ground beef	10^5 per g	Davis et al. 2010
Surface plasmon resonance	Pure culture	5×10^7 per mL	Fratamico et al. 1998
	Ground beef	3×10^3 per g	Wang et al. 2013
Electrochemiluminiscence	Pristine buffer Ground beef	10^2 - 2×10^2 per mL 10^3 - 2×10^3 per mL	Yu et al. 1996
	Spinach	10^4 per g	Leach et al. 2010

CFU: Colony Forming Unit; RT: Real-Time; ATP: Adenosine Triphosphate; PZT: Piezoelectric lead Zirconat Titanate; IMS: Immunomagnetic Separation; FT-IR: Fourier Transform Infrared

Table SM-1. Detection limits of E. coli O157:H7 using different rapid technologies.

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